

Data Dictionary

ALS Demographics and baseline data

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Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Document history/approvals
v1.1.1	03.12.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Review the document and suggest changes.
v1.1.0	03.12.2025	Adriano Chiò, Umberto Manera, Rosario Vasta, Carla D'Agostino, Alessandra Maccabeo	Review the Data Dictionary and address comments.
v1.0.1	19.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Format the document for HEREDITARY.
v1.0.0	01.01.2024	Adriano Chiò, Umberto Manera	Create the Data Dictionary.

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Description

This document provides the structured data dictionary for the ALS Demographics and baseline data collected at the University of Turin (UNITO), describing the variables and

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⁸ <https://ror.org/02catss52>

value definitions used in the cohort dataset. It is intended to accompany and document its Zenodo landing page.⁹

Variables	Description	Category	Notes
Patient ID	Unique identifier for each patient	Demographic	Identifier, not a clinical concept
Sex	Patient sex	Demographic	Male/Female/Other
Height	Height in centimeters	Demographic	Unit: centimeter
HBW	Healthy body weight	Demographic	Unit: kilogram
BMI_HBW	Body Mass Index at healthy body weight	Demographic	BMI calculated at healthy weight
W_diag	Weight at diagnosis	Demographic	Unit: kilogram
Marital_status	Marital status	Demographic	Categorical number 1.Single 2.Married 3.Separated 4.Divorced 5.Widow(er)
Education_years	Years of formal education	Demographic	Years
Cancer_ongoing	Ongoing at ALS diagnosis	Comorbidities	Yes/No
Cancer_type	Type of cancer	Comorbidities	Text. Specifies the cancer type
Hypertension	Hypertension status	Comorbidities	Yes/No
Thyroid	Thyroid disease	Comorbidities	Yes/No
Thyroid_type	Type of thyroid disease	Comorbidities	Text. Specifies the type of thyroid disease
Diabetes	Diabetes	Comorbidities	Yes/No
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Comorbidities	Yes/No
Cholecystectomy	History of	Comorbidities	Yes/No

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779232>

Variables	Description	Category	Notes
	gallbladder removal		
Asthma	Asthma	Comorbidities	Yes/No
Other disease	Any other comorbidities	Comorbidities	Free text / additional comorbidities
Smoke_diag	Smoking status at diagnosis	Comorbidities	Categorical number 1.Active 2.Former 3.Never
ALS_family_history	Family history of ALS	Disease	Yes/No
Onset_site	Anatomical site of ALS onset	Disease	Categorical number 1.Bulbar 2.Distal upper limbs 3.Proximal upper limbs 4.Distal lower limbs 5.Proximal lower limbs 6.Respiratory 7.Cognitive
Onset_side	Side of body where symptoms began	Disease	Categorical number 1.Right 2.Left 3.Bilateral
Onset_type	Type of symptom onset	Disease	Categorical number 1.Classical (UMN/LMN) 2.Pyramidal/PUMN 3.Prevalent LMN 4.Bulbar, prevalent LMN
Phenotype	ALS phenotype	Disease	Categorical number 1.Bulbar LMN 2.Bulbar UMN 3.Classical 4.Flail arm 5.Flail leg 6. Pyramidal/PUMN 7. Respiratory
Onset_age	Age at ALS symptoms onset	Disease	Numbers (years)
Diag_age	Age at ALS diagnosis	Disease	Numbers (years)
Diag_delay	Time from ALS onset to diagnosis	Disease	Numbers (months)

Variables	Description	Category	Notes
BMI_diag	BMI at ALS diagnosis	Disease	Unit: kilogram/meter ²
Cognitive evaluation	Cognitive evaluation performed	Disease	Yes/No
FTD_Strong_criteria	Frontotemporal dementia (Strong criteria ¹⁰)	Disease	Categorical number 1.CN (patients with normal cognition) 2.ALS-Ci (patients with cognitive impairment) 3.ALS-Bi (patients with behavioural impairment) 4.ALS-CBi (patients with cognitive and behavioural impairment) 5.ALS-FTD (patients with frontotemporal dementia)
PLS	Primary Lateral Sclerosis diagnosis	Disease	Yes/No
EL_diag	El Escorial Criteria ¹¹	Disease	Categorical number 1.Suspected 2.Possible 3.Probable with laboratory support 4. Probable 5. Definite
PEG	Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy	PEG	Yes/No
Age_PEG	Age at PEG placement	PEG	Numbers (years)
Onset_PEG	Time from onset to PEG	PEG	Numbers (months)
Diag_PEG	Time from diagnosis to PEG	PEG	Numbers (months)
PEG_death	Time from PEG placement to death	PEG	Numbers (months)
PEG_tracheo	Time from PEG placement to	PEG	Numbers (months)

¹⁰ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21678421.2016.1267768>

¹¹ doi: 10.1080/146608200300079536. PMID: 11464847

Variables	Description	Category	Notes
	tracheostomy		
NIV	Non-invasive ventilation	NIV	Yes/No
Age_NIV	Age at NIV initiation	NIV	Numbers (years)
Onset_NIV	Time from onset to NIV	NIV	Numbers (months)
Diag_NIV	Time from diagnosis to NIV	NIV	Numbers (months)
NIV_death	Time from NIV to death	NIV	Numbers (months)
NIV_tracheo	Time from NIV to tracheostomy	NIV	Numbers (months)
Tracheo	Tracheostomy	Tracheostomy	Yes/No
Age_tracheo	Age at tracheostomy	Tracheostomy	Numbers (years)
Onset_tracheo	Time from ALS onset to tracheostomy	Tracheostomy	Numbers (months)
Diag_tracheo	Time from diagnosis to tracheostomy	Tracheostomy	Numbers (months)
Tracheo_death	Time from tracheostomy to death	Tracheostomy	Numbers (months)
Surv_tot	Time from onset to death	Survival	Numbers (months)
Genetics	Genetic testing performed for the major ALS genes (C9orf72, SOD1, FUS, TARDBP) as part of diagnostic workup	Genetic testing	Yes/No
Genome	Genome analysis performed	Genetic testing	Yes/No
Genome_code	Genomic ID code	Genetic testing	Text

